

Research Article

"G-D's Physics" New Geulah Driven (CHCF) Model of the Universe's Origination, Sustenance & Development!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm based on a "time-sensitive" measurement of a predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days' time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish's e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, based upon its proven capacity to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistencies" that seem to exist between GRT & QM, replicate all major Relativistic & Quantum phenomena (ad laws) and is empirically validated based on two (unique) "Critical Predictions": the Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) associated with the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) two days' "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF special) time interval, and the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm was shown capable of completely unifying between GRT & QM, the Four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", for the first time in Physics!) and the Four Forces based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four physical features) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ (sec)}$ "! "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, principally negated the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "Big-Bang" Model, and associated (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, instead pointing at a novel "Universe's Six Days Origination" (USDO) Model! According to this USDO Model, this singular (higher-ordered) UCP has "pre-planned" the entire development of the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" and live accordingly. "G-D's Physics" new USDO Model is supported by the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction", and an urgent call if made to all Astronomers/Cosmologists to directly validate this UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction": "before"- "during"- and "subsequent" to the two days (Sep. 16th-17th) special CHCF time-interval! Significantly, Humanity is currently "entering" "G-D's Physics" validated "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state, e.g., with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics!

Introduction

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" (Computational Unified Field Theory, CUFT) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm;

One of the key discoveries stipulated by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}$ "! thereby producing an incredibly rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every minimal time-point [1-47].

Indeed, one of the key differences between the Old "Material-Causal"

Paradigm and the New "G-D's Physics' A-Causal Computation" Paradigm is the fundamental realization, whereby there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! Rather, the sole manner in which the entire physical universe (e.g., or indeed any smaller "Physical System" found within this physical universe) "exists" and "evolves" – is solely based on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) production of the (extremely rapid) series of UF's frame/s! Thus, for instance, previous articles have indicated that this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negated (in principle) the feasibility of GRT's "Big-Bang Model"! This is because since this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels

existing in any (consecutive) UF's frame/s! Moreover, since all of these exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore there also cannot exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in different UF's frame/s! Hence, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT assuming that an initial Big-Bang "nuclear event" "caused" the creation of all of the "matter", "energy", "space", "time", all of the galaxies, stars, planets etc. in the universe is strictly negated by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm!

Hence, we see that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – either "during" any consecutive UF's frame/s or "in-between" them! Moreover, according to two profound new Theoretical Postulates of this New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm, entitled: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and the (closely related) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) the only "constant", "uniform" and "continuous" principle that exists both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames is this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP/UCR) that manifests as the physical universe "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but remains solely and singularly "in-between" any two UF's frame/s!

Indeed, it may be said that there is a stark contrast between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (e.g., underlying both GRT & QM) and the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm in terms of their basic assumption regarding the origin- true nature- and "purpose"- of the existence of the entire physical universe! According to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, the origination of the entire physical universe is assumed to have been "caused" by a (random) initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, it evolves merely based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and their assumed "causing" of a "curvature of Space-Time" (and conversely, the determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive objects" and other "less-massive" objects is strictly "caused" by this "curvature of Space-Time"); and it "drifting" towards an "Entropic State" of a complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe, and all of its Suns, Galaxies, planets etc... In contrast, according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the entire origination- and continuous "dissolution", re-creation and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the physical universe has been "pre-planned", and evolved based on the "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP) plan to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" state through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Perfected Geulah State" in which the singularity of this "All-Goodness", "Moral", "Peace" and "Harmony" (characterized) UCR will be recognized by Science and Humanity, thereby leading Humanity towards this "Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, in which Humanity will lead a life characterized by these ("sublime") characteristics of "Morality", "Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

"G-D's Physics" Twenty-First Century's Paradigmatic-Shift

Scientific Inquiry (within any given discipline) is governed by empirical data and logical reasoning that can best explain that given data within a cohesive Theoretical Framework! However, the famous Philosopher of Science, Thomas Kuhn taught us that the evolution of such Scientific Inquiry (within a given scientific discipline) alternates between phases governed by a given "Standard Paradigm" in which such a given "Standard Paradigm" is capable of explaining all known data and phenomena, and an inevitable subsequent "Paradigmatic-Shift" into a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which follows the appearance of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" within the Old "Standard Paradigm"; Such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is characterized by the appearance of "theoretical inconsistencies" between the "foundations" of the Old "Standard Paradigm", such as for instance the apparent the-

oretical inconsistency that appeared between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory. In addition, a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is also characterized by the principle inability of this Old "Standard Paradigm" to account for a key empirical phenomenon, such the inability of the Old 19th century's Newtonian Mechanics to empirically validate the existence of the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept which was key for Newtonian Mechanical Theoretical Framework?! Kuhn teaches us that alongside with the appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" for the Old "Standard Paradigm" (in this case Newtonian Mechanics) there emerges the "New Paradigm" (e.g., Relativity Theory) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" (between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory), resolving the "unexplained empirical phenomenon" (e.g., Relativity Theory discarded the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept as "superfluous" or "non-existent!"); and most significantly identify and empirically validate at least one unique "Critical Prediction" of the "New Paradigm" – as more valid than the corresponding prediction of the "Old Paradigm": In the case of Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) this unique "Critical Prediction" related to his prediction regarding the double-valued curvature of Mercury's perihelion's pathway around the Sun (e.g., due to the Sun's mass' curvature of Space-Time affecting Mercury's curved perihelion pathway); Indeed, once Einstein's double-valued Mercury's perihelion pathway (around the Sun) unique "Critical Prediction" was validated by Eddington during the famous 1919 Solar Eclipse – Einstein's GRT "triumphed" and was accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm for 20th century Theoretical Physics!

We stand at an equivalent (historic) "juncture" in which the Old "Material-Causal" (Standard Paradigm) of GRT and Quantum Mechanics (QM), has reached a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis", e.g., due the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between these two GRT & QM "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm seem "theoretically inconsistent": this is due to the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) for the transmission of any signal (or information) across space and time, as opposed to QM's (empirically validated) "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon which indicates that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (space-energy, time-mass) value/s, e.g., apparently contradicting GRT's SLB fundamental constraint?! Additionally, there exists a key "unexplained empirical phenomenon" relating to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion which can only be explained by GRT's assuming of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts which are assumed to comprise up to 90% of all the mass and energy in the universe – but yet failed to be detected (despite numerous experimental attempts) for the past two decades?! Indeed, two highly influential scientific articles recently published by Scientific American begin questioning the validity of these purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts! (REF??). Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT and QM has reached a state of "Paradigmatic-Crisis" which has indeed led to the discovery of a New "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT), recently termed: "G-D's Physics" (See exhaustive Bentovish References) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM!

The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – at an unfathomably rapid rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)!" This produces an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such "minimal time point", e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each con-

secutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{1 \dots n \dots \infty\} [Px]_{\{a \dots z\}} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and

integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:
 $S: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}) \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {0-x,0-y,0-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i \dots n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {0-x,0-y,0-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i \dots n\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}) \{UF(i \dots n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h [UF's (i...n)]$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ($E = Mc^2$) and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels - "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe - regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly - both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: c) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole

evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that King Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" - prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" - through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of some of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" - based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" - "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" - "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה")

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe - which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past" - "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order

to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Chessed"/חֶסֶד):

this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חֶסֶד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/גבורה):

denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of mul-

multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

the sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predic-

tions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת"/"Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol of "ניצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תשובה")/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva"/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting ob

jects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinity ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the

"Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinity ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinity ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec') for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: \{O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i) - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)\} \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54,56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [54,56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" elec-

tron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [53,57], higher dimension gravity, [48], a new boson, [52] and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [51], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [58-61]. This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two

(abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

We therefore reach major "Paradigmatic-Shift" and basic "turning-point" in our fundamental understanding of the origin- true nature- and even "purpose" of the creation of the entire physical universe! Based on the unequivocal validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions, we must accept "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm! It signifies a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm because it points at the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the same- or different-UF's frame/s – due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (back into the singularity of the UCP!) Indeed, based on the direct empirical validation of (two abovementioned) unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm to the New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm – which (inevitably) brings about a fundamental "metamorphosis" in our basic understanding of the true nature, origin and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, i.e., based on the UCP's (singular higher-ordered "preplanned") "Blueprint Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings towards the UCP's preplanned "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace & Harmony" and "steering" the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"!

This fundamental "metamorphosis" in "G-D's Physics" basic understanding of the true nature, dynamics, development and even "Ultimate Goal" of the universe, i.e., leading to its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" is characterized by several key elements:

a) Negation of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships (e.g.,

including: the "Big-Bang" Model, Einstein's GRT & QM's "Material-Causal" basic assumption & "Darwin's Natural Selection Process" (DNSP) Evolutionary Theory). As shown previously shown, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of all of those exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s (back into the singularity of this UCP) negate (in principle) the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's "material-causal" basic assumption, pertaining to the existence of (direct or even indirect) physical relationship/s between certain relativistic or quantum elements that give rise to the various phenomena in the physical universe!? Since the UCP "simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's – with their complete "dissolution" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s! In this manner, it's been (previously)

demonstrated that this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negates the very possibility of the existence of the "Big-Bang" initially assumed nuclear event because there could not have existed any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between this (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its (assumed) creation of any sun/s, galaxies, planets, mass or energy in the universe (in any single or multiple UF's frame/s!) In much the same manner, "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm was shown to negate QM's (assumed) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any subatomic "probe" and "target" elements which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of the "target's (assumed) probability wave-function" into a single (complimentary) "energy-mass" or "space-time" value!? Once again, there could not exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any subatomic "probe" and "target" elements (in any single- or multiple- UF's frames)!?

b) Realization of the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" underlying & transcending the physical universe, (e.g., including through e "Computational Duality Principle, CDP)!

Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm proves that there can only exist one singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, while principally negating the basic "material-causal" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) (e.g., underlying GRT, QM & DNSP)! CDP???

Indeed, based upon this principal negation of the CDP of the basic "material-causal" computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT, QM (& DNSP Evolutionary Theory), this leads to the recognition of the singularity of the UCP – i.e., as underlying all relativistic, quantum and DNSP relationships)! Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (novel) Theoretical Postulates, it is realized that the only "computationally-invariant" element in the universe is this "UCP" since it is the only element that exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame's exhaustive spatial pixels (four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"), as well as solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! In contrast, the entire physical universe (including all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) only exists "during" each (consecutive) UF's frame/s computation by this singular ("computationally-invariant") UCP, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s?! Therefore, the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm assert that only this singular higher-ordered ("computationally-invariant") UCP may be considered as "constant", "continuous" and "real" whereas the whole universe (and of all of its exhaustive spatial pixels' four physical features) may only be seen as "computationally invariant", e.g., as existing only "phenomenally" and "transiently"! In fact, according to the "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate, the whole physical universe is seen as only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR!

c) The UCP's Complete Integration (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) of the Four basic Physical Features, GRT & QM (and Four Forces) based on the newly discovered "UCP's Universal Computational Formula"

Another significant accomplishment of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm regards its complete integration (for the first time in Theoretical Physics!) between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based upon "G-D's Physics" discovery of the UCP's (two out of three) Computational Dimensions, e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent") whose four possible combinations yield those four basic physical features – as com-

pletely integrated within "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF):

FIGURE 2: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [Px]_(a...z)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O_{(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

$$n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O_{(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n) \leq c * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM!

d) "G-D's Physics" Revision of GRT's "Space-Time Curvature" by "Massive Objects"!

Another key new understanding arising from the discovery of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is its ability to resolve the "Gravitational Enigma": Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm); Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and

“independent”) of the Standard Model’s proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles’ interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved “Gravitational Enigma”?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this “Gravitational Enigma” (GE) based on the discovery of a New “G-d’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm[1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this “Gravitational Enigma” (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ”), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”! Additionally, the UCP’s simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF’s frame/s yields the UCP’s novel “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two “Computational Dimensions” of “Framework” and “Consistency! According to this (new) G-D’S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the “mass” value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those “Framework” (e.g., “frame” or “object”) and “Consistency” (“consistent” or “inconsistent”) “Computational Dimensions”: Such that the UCP computes “Framework” – “consistent” vs. “inconsistent” computations, as the “space” and “energy” values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF’s); and “Object” – “consistent” or “inconsistent” computations, as the “mass” and “time” values (across a given UF’s series) (Figure 1):

FIGURE 1: UCP’S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
<u>Consistent</u>	<u>“Space”</u>	<u>“Mass”</u>
<u>Inconsistent</u>	<u>“Energy”</u>	<u>“Time”</u>

Intriguingly, these novel “G-D’S PHYSICS” UCP’s “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an “Universal Computational Formula” (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational “by-products” of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

Figure 2: The “UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA” (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} s \\ e \end{array} \right\} * \left. \begin{array}{c} t \\ m \end{array} \right\}$$

UF’s {n...n...n} [PxI (a...z)] t * m

Note: which is accompanied by “G-D’S PHYSICS” computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”. in which “Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle’s” (“complimentary pairs”) are embedded as “special cases” within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of “G-D’S PHYSICS” or G-D’S PHYSICS).

The UCF’s Relativistic Format”

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} E * s \\ t \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} M * c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\}$$

in which GRT’s (famous) “Energy-Mass Equivalence” is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF’s Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} t * m \\ s * e \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} h * \\ c^2 \end{array} \right\}$$

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm’s potential resolution of the GE’s first component – i.e., a) *Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of “gravitation” which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP’s (in-depth) analysis of the (true) “computational basis” of the “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D’S PHYSICS’s computational analysis, this “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” for the transmission of any “signal” (or even “information”) across “space” and “time” – which seems to be “contradicted” by QM’s “Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon”, indicating that the measurement of one “entangled particle” “instantaneously” affects the “complimentary” (“space/energy” or “mass/time”) measurement of the other “entangled particle”?! But, according to the new CUT’s Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and “resolution”- of this apparent “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from the UCP’s singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all “Single Spatial-Temporal” computation (“SST”): “particle” of relativistic “object” (e.g., relating to only “one” spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), “Multi Spatial-Temporal” computation (MST): “wave” (e.g., relating to at least “two” points being measured at any point in time) or “Exhaustive Spatial Temporal” (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all “exhaustive” spatial pixels comprising an entire “Universal Frame”, UF), across a series of UF’s frames (Figure 3);*

FIGURE 3: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

e) Negation of the "Big-Bang Model" & "Einstein's Equations' Material-Causal Assumption"!

Indeed, once we begin realizing that the entire physical universe exists only as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) (e.g., since it only exists "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s as solely computed by this singular UCR but "dissolves" back into the UCR's singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); and that (in fact) there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) relativistic or quantum (subatomic) exhaustive spatial pixels (found within the same-or different- UF's frame/s); we have to revise some of the basic "material-causal" assumptions standing as the very "basis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM!

Thus, for instance, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT, which assumes that the entire physical universe was "caused" or "created" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" ("space" and "time") of the entire physical universe – was shown to be questioned and (in fact) negated by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is simply because if (indeed) this singular (higher-ordered) UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36\text{-}50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$), and "dissolves" back into the UCR singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, then there could not have been any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the first- second-... or "trillionth" UF's frame/s – which implies that the "Big-Bang" nuclear event could not have occurred, i.e., at least as "causing" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" etc. in the universe! The only thing that could have happened is the UCR's consecutive computation of a series of UF's frames that evolved- and is (in fact) still evolving the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising it) – e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": "plants", "animals" and "human-beings" towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

In order to better grasp this new "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm a "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" has been illustrated: depicting an imaginary "film-scenario", in which a "mercury-ball" is shown to impact a "glass-jar" (filled with water) which seems to "cause" the breakage of this "glass-jar" (and consequent "spillage of water")... But (in fact), when we "slow-down" (and even "halt") the progression of this "Cinematic-Film Metaphor", and closely examine each of these consecutive "film-frames" (separately), we can clearly discern that at each (consecutive) film-frame, all of its exhaustive spatial pixels are being depicted "simultaneously" – so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) spatial pixels comprising each of these (consecutive) film-frames! We also realize that there cannot exist any such "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two consecutive film-frames (e.g., or in fact any two film-frames)! This is simply due to the fact that "in-between" any two such film-frames transpires a "pure-light" (of the "projector") so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect

"physical interaction" between any of the (exhaustive) spatial pixels comprising one "film-frame" and any other subsequent "film-frame"! Therefore, we realize that despite the "appearance" of a "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury ball" and its apparent "impact" upon the "glass-jar" – which seemed to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" (and "spillage" of water); the only thing that really "exists" is the arrangement of this series of "film-frames" depicting an (ever-closer) "proximity" of the "mercury ball" and "glass-jar" until their "conjoining" (e.g., being presented as "touching" each other) which then leads to the presentation of a broken "glass-jar" and "spillage of water"... Hence, we must realize that despite the appearance of a direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury-ball" and ("water-filled") "glass-jar" (which seems to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" - and "spillage" of "water") – in reality, there is only an "arrangement" of this series of "film-frames" in a manner which gives us the "impression" (or "perception") of such a "material-causal" relationship between the "mercury-ball" and its "breakage" of the "glass-jar"...

Indeed, based on this (simple yet profound) "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" we can clearly understand that in the same manner that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in (any) two film-frames (e.g., due to the "simultaneous" presentation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given "film-frame" and the complete "dissolution" of all the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given "film-frame/s" into the "pure-light" separating between any two such consecutive "film-frames"); there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive") "universal Frames" (comprising the entire physical universe at any given "minimal time-point")! Therefore, the "material-causal" assumption underlying the "Big-Bang" Model (emanating from Einstein's GRT) is strictly negated based on this New Twenty-First Century's "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) simply because this "Big-Bang Model" precisely assumes such "material-causal" (direct) physical interactions between an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its "causing" (or "creation") of all the "suns", "galaxies", "matter" and "energy" ("space" and "time") in the physical universe – which is strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (consecutive) UF's (and the complete "dissolution" of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels into the singularity of the "Universal Computational Reality", "UCR" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!)

An important computational basis for this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm are two of its former Theoretical Postulates called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) and associated "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which state that it is not possible (in principle) for any two given computational elements ("x") and ("y") to determine (or "cause") the value/s of one of these elements (i.e., "y") – because such a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) would inevitably lead to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted by that Computational System's proven (empirical) capacity to determine the given 'y' element's values: Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicitly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" SRCS: it is assumed that it is only based on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec")! Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm: SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Uec-aer" or "Not Uec-aer "

But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome": SRCNS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Not Uec-aer" In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-aer ("Not Uec-aer"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-aer rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-aer" (increased) rate of expansion!?! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRNC System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-aer or subsequent Not Uec-aer state of the universe's acceleration rate exists?! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER) – then this would negate the SRNC assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNC computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRCNS: {DM/DE, Uec-er } ti → {"Not Uec-er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNC computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti : as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec-er at ti+n ?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCNS(SRNC) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be " Uec-er" (at ti) or " Not Uec-er" (at ti+n) ?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNC Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c² /h"

= 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec⁻¹), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal timepoint"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCEAR) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)!

f) Centrality of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" & associated Earth's Functional Center of the Universe!

So, we realize that the "curvature of Space-time" is not "caused" by any "massive-objects", but is rather the result of the UCP's differential presentation of "High-Energy, Low-Mass" (HELM) vs. "High-Mass, Low Energy" (HMLE) exhaustive spatial pixels – which gives us the "impression", wherein those HELM remain "consistent" across a series of UF's frames, as opposed to the other LMHE exhaustive spatial pixels which do not remain "constant" across a series of UF's frames, thereby giving rise to our perception of the HMLE "curving Space-time"?! When we connect this new "G-D's Physics" realization that the "curvature of Space-Time" is not "caused" by the presence of any "massive objects" (e.g., but rather can be explained by the UCP's differential computation of certain HMLE vs. HELM exhaustive spatial pixels regions etc., as explained above and previously); together with "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's negation of the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), then this leads to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis" (RTGGH) theoretical postulate, which postulates that the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" from its "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" – "backwards" towards the beginning of the universe, e.g., so that this UCP has "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the fulfillment of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe! This "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the universe is a state in which Humanity and Science recognize the singularity of the UCP – as comprising the sole and singular reality underlying the physical universe and "steering" it towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe etc.!

In other words, we realize that since according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, and therefore that there cannot exist any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interactions or effects across any series of UF's frame/s; therefore, "G-D's Physics" RTGGH postulate asserts that the whole origination- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel within it) is based on the UCP's "pre-planned" "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" plan to advance the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state – but could not be based upon any ("random") "material-causal" physical interaction/s, e.g., including (as shown above), "G-D's Physics" strict negation of the "Big-Bang" Model, as well as the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion! In other words, we perceive the great "beauty" "internal-consistency" and "elegance" found within "G-D's Physics" new alternative conception of the whole origination- sustenance- development- and fulfillment- of the UCP's "pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of "steering" the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the fulfillment of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the universe (and Humanity and Science)! However, such a profound (totally) new understanding of the true nature

of the entire physical universe – as representing only a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular UCR (which alone can be considered as the "constant", "consistent" and "uniform" singular true reality underlying and indeed transcending the physical universe) questions and challenges (and even negates) some of the basic (and most fundamental) assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! This is because we realize that not only the universe could not have been created (or "caused") by the (previously) assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (as explained above and previously due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all of those exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames!) Likewise, the continues (accelerated) expansion of the universe could not be explained by the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts or by the "Cosmological Constant", or in fact based on any of those three "Exceptional Expulsive Elements" (EEE's) associated with Einstein's Equations of General Relativity Theory (GRT), based on "G-D's Physics" CDP's detailed analysis and negation of the basic "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS) characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's fundamental Computational Systems' structure!

But, if in fact, there truly exists only one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP), and there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, then we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the whole origination- ("dissolution"-) "sustenance"- and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety!) is solely dependent upon the (previously outlined) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) associated with this singular UCP/UCR (which is also presented through the below "THCD's-UCF" Formula, and the accompanying Diagram):

Based on the results obtained, which indicate that there are at least two unique Critical Predictions of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (GRT's & QM's) corresponding predictions, we must embrace the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm as "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! In fact, as demonstrated previously, we see that this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) embeds and incorporates key elements of the Old GRT & QM Paradigm as "special-cases" within the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, based on the discovery of "G-D's Physics" novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), e.g., including its two Relativistic & Quantum Formats!

So, the question becomes: what is the key factor that "causes" the universe to accelerate its expansion rate, i.e., both in terms of the greater acceleration of relatively more distant galactic elements, and in terms of the increase (with time) of the universe's expansion rate? Based upon the unequivocal support of the abovementioned empirical findings regarding the UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion (over time) – which fulfils a unique "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm pointing at the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" increase in the UCP's singular (higher-ordered) universe's rate of expansion, e.g., during such special times as the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) two days' time interval, then this unequivocally points at UCP's increase in the universe's expansion – i.e., as "triggered" by the UNCIARE-JRH!

Obviously, a further direct empirical validation of the specific UNCIARE increase during those two days of the JRH: this year scheduled to occur during Sep. 16th & 17th would add an eve greater certainty to the already existent empirical validation of the UCP's increase of the universe's rate of acceleration as ensued by the JRH's Collective Human Consciousness Focus! But regardless of this further empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century), it is becom-

ing clear that it is this CHCF which "triggers" the singular higher-ordered UCP to increase the rate of the universe's expansion rate! However, if indeed, it is this CHCF that "triggers" the UCP's increase in its UNCIARE rate of the universe's expansion; which we've already seen increases over the universe's entire course of evolution, e.g., as indicated by "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH resolution of the (otherwise "unresolved" Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (CAGUARE)); then this implies that it is critical that this CHCF should affect the universe's UNCIARE-JRH from the beginning of the universe – and continuously till this present JRH New Year's two days' special time-interval?!

Revising Our Time-Scaling of the Universe!

The basic "time-scaling" of the universe according to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm assumes that every phenomenon in the universe can be explained simply based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain physical elements; Hence, the "Big-Bang" Model assumes that the universe was created (or "caused") by an initial "nuclear event" that created all of the suns, galaxies, matter and energy in the universe. More generally, as noted above, GRT's explanation of the continuous accelerated expansion of the universe depends on Einstein's Equations' (three) "Exceptional-Expulsive Elements" (EE's) including the "Big-Bang" event, "Cosmological Factor" and (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" concepts – all based on a direct physical interaction between certain physical elements, which is assumed to "cause" the universe's expansion; Specifically, the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is assumed to be "caused" by such a direct physical interaction between those (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) and certain galactic elements. accelerated expansion! But, since all hitherto scientific experiments aiming to directly validate the existence of those "elusive" DM/DE (purely hypothetical) concepts have failed to do so! Moreover (as indicated above), "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including between those (purely hypothetical) DM/DE concepts and any other galactic elements, e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single (or multiple UF's frames), and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! More generally, Einstein's Equations (three) EE's are also negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, once again, because each of these (three) EE's relies on the same basic "material-causal" assumption wherein there exists certain direct physical interaction/s, e.g., (a) between the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of all the suns, galaxies, energy and mass in the universe etc. (b) between the assumed "Cosmological Constant" and the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion. (c) as noted, between the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" and certain galactic elements.

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the fundamental "material-causal" assumption of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm assuming that the universe was created by such an assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and evolving based on a (hypothetical) "Cosmological Constant" and (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts – are all strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) because there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different-UF's frame/s, due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, according to the two additional (profound) theoretical postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, e.g., the "Computational Invariance Princi-

ple" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), the universe does not exist as an "independent", "constant" or "continuous" phenomenon, but rather represents a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the singular (higher ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists both "during" its simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! (This is because according to the "Computational Invariance Principle" only this singular UCP/UCR may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", existing constantly and uniformly both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s and "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; whereas the entire physical universe, and its four basic physical features of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass" pertaining to every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe only represent "computationally-variant" elements that exist only as computed simultaneously for each consecutive UF's frame/s by this UCP, but "cease to exist" and "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s?!) Therefore, the only existing "computationally-invariant reality" is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) that exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Hence, if we wish to understand the "origination", "sustenance" and "evolution" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety!) so many "trillions" of times each second (e.g., $c^2/h = 1.35^{50}$), then we must analyze this singular higher-ordered "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions", and its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF). This is because once we realize that the whole entire physical universe exists only as a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR); and that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s; therefore we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein it is only based on a deeper understanding of the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular higher-ordered UCR that we can begin understanding the whole "origination", "sustenance" and "evolution" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as its "Ultimate Geulah Goal" state of the universe, as been outlined previously and summarized below:

The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

11) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

12) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

13) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת):

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and

human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

14) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Chessed"/חסד):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

15)The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/גבורה):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings'

"moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

16) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Tiferet"/תפארת):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension" – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm

of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification-or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

17) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח" "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

18) The "Teshuva" (תשובה)"/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

19) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however,

that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

20) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec) for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

**Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS'
UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):**

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion!?) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "ma-

terial-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

URE 2: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Intriguingly, based on the discovery of these THCD's characteristics of the operation of this singular higher-ordered UCR (and associated THCD's-UCF), we realize that the whole "origination", "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "preplanned" by this singular higher-ordered UCR in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter form through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state of the universe, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, and its THCD's ("sublime") characteristics including: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also typify Humanity's Perfected "Geulah Goal" State (behavior and attitude towards each other etc.)! According to this New "G-D's Physics" THCD's Geulah-Goal Directed Universe's theoretical perspective, the universe was not created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor has its evolution been the result of any ("random": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including its (abovementioned) negation of the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, or "Cosmological Constant" etc.; but rather as originating from the UCP's/UCR's "preplanned Blueprint Plan" to develop the universe from its "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe! In order to perhaps (further) elucidate this novel conception of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, we can utilize the "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" (which has been used previously) to explain this new conception of the universe's development: If we were to imagine a certain "action-film" such as "James Bond's" famous films, we could envision a whole "cascade of events" in which James Bond escapes "grave dangers" in order to protect the "vital interests" of his government (and the whole free world), ultimately leading to the abolishment of the "evil organization" trying to sabotage "world-peace", and fulfillment of such a desired "World-Peace Agreement" that would advance Humanity towards a "cooperative, peaceful and prosperous future"... But, if we analyze (deeper) this Cinematic-Film Metaphor scenario, we could see that the whole progression and "plot" of the film has been "pre-planned" before the "shooting" of the film! In fact, we could not imagine any "occurrence" taking place within the film which would "affect" or "alter" this "pre-planned plot" of the film, nor any "interactions" occurring within the film! On the contrary, we realize that all of these (apparently) "random occurrences" were "pre-planned" by the producer of the film in order to lead us (the "viewers" of the film) to realize a certain "motto" of this ("thrilling") "James Bond Action Film" – i.e., such as: to believe that there is always a "good-ending" in Life, and that "good prevails"! In much the same manner, it is suggested that this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, and therefore that the whole "origination", "sustenance" and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole physical universe) develops solely based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's (preplanned) "Perfected Geulah Goal Directed Universe" Blueprint Plan!

In other words, we must embrace an entirely new conception of the entire "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the physical universe: which was not created by an initial "random Big-Bang" nuclear event, or that is being expanded (at an accelerated rate) by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts; Instead the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm explains the whole "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe (as well as of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) solely based on the fulfillment of the UCP's/UCR's preplanned "Blueprint Plan" for a "Geulah Perfected Goal Driven Universe"! Therefore, instead of assuming that the universe was created by a random initial ("Big-Bang") nuclear event (which

is assumed to have "caused" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy in the universe); and moreover (based on this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle", DNSP – which were all negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" empirically validated Scientific Paradigm) that the various Biological forms' evolution on Earth were also created by "random" "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "genetically-mutated" organisms and a "challenging environment" etc.; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm stipulates that the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – all leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR and behaving in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

Moreover, based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which is dependent upon the (stipulated) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) (e.g., of Millions of Jews praying and focusing on this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., in religious terms: "G-D")! therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm it is clear that the increase in the universe's accelerated expansion rate (e.g., manifesting through the otherwise unexplained abovementioned CAGUARE phenomenon) – is contingent upon the existence of such CHCF (UNCAIRE-JRH) every consecutive year, from the very "beginning" of the universe and up till today! In other words, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the whole evolution and expansion of the entire physical universe – and specifically the (otherwise unexplained CAGUARE phenomenon) critically depends upon the CHCF associated with the JRH's UNCIARE (e.g., empirically validated by "G-D's Physics" Critical UNCIARE prediction above, and urgent call for Astronomers testing of the specific UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's expansion accelerated rate during the upcoming JRH on the 16th-17th of Sep., 2023!) This means that according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's (empirically validated) CHCF, and associated THCD's-UCF (which delineates the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes every consecutive UF's frame/s at the unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1/36^{50}$ sec!"), it is hereby stipulated that the UCP's/UCR's initial "origination" of the whole universe – including its complete "progression" from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings took place in only six (or seven) days (i.e., to include the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State")!

This is because it is only "logical" to assume that if the UCP/UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec!)" by employing specifically those seven HCD's which are computing and "materializing" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (based on the Three Initial Key HCD's which together comprise the THCD's!); and if indeed (as proven empirically through "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction") the continuous increase in the universe's expansion rate critically depended upon the presence of human-beings and their capacity to carry out this CHCF-JRH for each consecutive years since the UCR's "origination" of the universe (e.g., till the current time); therefore, it is "logical" to assume that the UCR has created the whole universe based on its seven HCD's (e.g., corresponding HCD for each day!)

Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Six Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due

to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Severn Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

1) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

2) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ")

3) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Compu-

tational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

4) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

5) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination" - "sustenance" - and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

6) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)!

7) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF

that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

8) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec") based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion! "G-D's Physics" New Geulah Driven (CHCF) Model of the Universe's Origination & Development!

So, we've reached a very important (historic) "turning-point" in our basic understanding of the whole origination- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical, based on a "pre-planned" "Geulah Driven" Blueprint Plan of the UCP (singular reality) towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe and Humanity! Based upon the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions" (e.g., as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM) we must accept "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm as the New for the Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! As we've seen, this implies that the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption wherein the universe was "created" (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, as well as the (accelerated) expansion of the universe as "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts – were strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) due to the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s) due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP!) In the same manner it's been shown that this "G-D's Physics" new "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (and associated "Computational Duality Principle", CDP) also negates "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle" (DNSP) Evolutionary Theory (e.g., also due to its basically assumed "material-causal" physical interactions etc.);

"G-D's Physics" alternative new (and exciting) "Universe's Six Days Origination" (USDO) Model of the universe which is based on its "Geulah Driven Development Universe" conception, and the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" (above) offers an entirely new conception of the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of the entire physical universe! This new USDO "Geulah Driven Model of the universe is based on "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis" postulate which postulates that the whole development of the universe has been "pre-planned" by the "Universal Computational/Consciousness

Principle" (or UCR) in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through the "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" of the universe – in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside its "intrinsic" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! Taken together with the empirically validated UNCIARE (JRH) increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – as associated with the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF at the JRH: i.e., with the special urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to empirically validate this more specific UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th-17th, 2023) as evidenced by the (otherwise) "unexplained" "Astronomical-Cosmological Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (ACGUARE) (e.g., which cannot be explained by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion associated with the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" that could not be validated for the past two full decades despite intensive experimental efforts to do so?! "G-D's Physics" USDP conception of the "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the universe points at the UCP's/UCR's creation and development of all "inanimate" matter and "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings in a mere six initial days' time-interval (as stipulated by the USDO) e.g., as plausible based on the fact that we see that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm offers a satisfactory explanation for the (otherwise "unexplained") ACGUARE phenomenon based upon "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" theoretical postulate!

In other words, since we see that the universe cannot contain any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s (between any two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, and could not therefore have been created by an (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could it be expanded by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts (which also rely on such negated "material-interactions"); we must embrace the alternative new conception of "G-D's Physics" USDO Model of the "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of the universe – as being pre-planned based on the UCP's "Geulah-Driven" plan for advancing the universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, all leading to the Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the singularity of this UCP/UCR, and being characterized by its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" and its "steering" of Humanity towards this Perfected Geulah Goal State! In fact, this (novel) "G-D's Physics" USDO precisely delineates the manner in which the UCP/UCR has created the entire physical universe in a mere six days initial interval – based on its six (key secondary) HCD's (e.g., with each one of them being devoted for one day respectively), which has led to the creation of a human-being in the sixth day! This is necessary for "G-D's Physics" novel discovery of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" postulate wherein the whole development of the universe's accelerated rate of expansion is entirely dependent upon this CHCF taking place at each consecutive year, e.g., from its origination till this upcoming JRH expected UNCIARE (whose empirical validation is, once again, called for all Astronomers/Cosmologists, see initial Note!)

So, we realize that for the universe to evolve there must have existed this CHCF from the culmination of the very first six days (e.g., except that at that time the first human-being executed this CHCF together with the entire creation – perhaps as a "preview" for the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"), which we are now "entering", with "G-D's Physics" recognition of the singularity of the UCP/UCR, its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" and "Perfected Geulah State" in which Humanity begins living in accordance with these "sublime" characteristics!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" empirical validation of the UCP's UNCIARE (JRH) indicate that the universe's increase in its accelerated rate of expansion - e.g., "in time", occurs based on this CHCF

every year during the two days' special time-interval of the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH New Year) as evinced by the (otherwise "unexplained") ACQUARE phenomenon! Likewise, it was postulated by "G-D's Physics" that this CHCF is also responsible for the universe's accelerated expansion – "in space", i.e., manifesting in the accelerated increase in the farthest regions of galactic expansion, relative to the "closer" regions of the universe – relative to Earth's CHCF! This has led to the recognition of the Earth's CHCF as the "functional center" of the entire physical universe, since it is from this Earth's CHCF "functional epicenter" that the entire physical universe accelerates its expansion rate, both "in time" (at every consecutive year's JRH CHCF's two days special time-interval), and "in space" (e.g., with the furthest "galactic regions" expanding at an accelerated rate, relative to the closest regions to Earth's CHCF)! Hence, the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm actually transforms Humanity's state into the "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" in which Humanity and Science recognize the singularity of this UCP and begin living in accordance with its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc.!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to my dear beloved (diseased) Mother Dr. Tizrach (Bat Yitzchak) Bentwich whose faith and encouragement have allowed me to discover and develop this profound "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Physics!

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